

Machine Learning-Derived Active Sleep as an Early Predictor of White Matter Development in Preterm Infants

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White matter dysmaturation is commonly seen in preterm infants admitted to the neonatal intensive care unit (NICU). Animal research has shown that active sleep is essential for early brain plasticity. This study aimed to determine the potential of active sleep as an early predictor for subsequent white matter development in preterm infants. Using heart and respiratory rates routinely monitored in the NICU, we developed a machine learning-based automated sleep stage classifier in a cohort of 25 preterm infants (12 females). The automated classifier was subsequently applied to a study cohort of 58 preterm infants (31 females) to extract active sleep percentage over 5–7 consecutive days during 29–32 weeks of postmenstrual age. Each of the 58 infants underwent high-quality T2-weighted magnetic resonance brain imaging at term-equivalent age, which was used to measure the total white matter volume. The association between active sleep percentage and white matter volume was examined using a multiple linear regression model adjusted for potential confounders. Using the automated classifier with a superior sleep classification performance [mean area under the receiver operating characteristic curve (AUROC) = 0.87, 95% CI 0.83–0.92], we found that a higher active sleep percentage during the preterm period was significantly associated with an increased white matter volume at term-equivalent age [$\beta = 0.31$, 95% CI 0.09–0.53, false discovery rate (FDR)-adjusted p -value = 0.021]. Our results extend the positive association between active sleep and early brain development found in animal research to human preterm infants and emphasize the potential benefit of sleep preservation in the NICU setting.

Key words: automated sleep stage classification; preterm sleep; white matter development

Significance Statement

Preterm infants face a high risk of white matter abnormalities. Evidence from animal studies has highlighted the crucial role that active sleep plays in early brain development. This study examined the association between artificial intelligence-derived active sleep and white matter development in human preterm infants admitted to the neonatal intensive care unit (NICU). The results revealed that preterm infants with higher active sleep percentages during their NICU stay exhibited significantly larger white matter volumes at term-equivalent age. Our findings suggest the potential benefits of safeguarding sleep, particularly active sleep, in the NICU. By incorporating automated sleep monitoring into routine caregiving practices, caregivers can tailor elective care according to an infant's sleep cycles, thereby promoting optimal early brain development.

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Introduction

Over recent decades, advancements in obstetric and neonatal management have substantially improved the survival chances of preterm infants admitted to the neonatal intensive care unit (NICU) (Costeloe et al., 2012; Ancel et al., 2015; Patel, 2016). Nonetheless, these infants still face a high risk of white matter abnormalities, such as volume loss and ventricular dilatation, which can be detected by magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) at term-equivalent age (Dubois et al., 2014; Volpe, 2019). Follow-up studies have revealed that these abnormalities are often associated

with long-term neurodevelopmental impairments (Woodward et al., 2006; Northam et al., 2011; Anderson et al., 2017).

Numerous animal studies have provided evidence that sleep, especially active sleep, plays a vital role in early brain development (Graven, 2006; Blumberg et al., 2020; Park, 2020; Knoop et al., 2021; Lokhandwala and Spencer, 2022). Active sleep, also known as rapid eye movement sleep, is characterized by rapid eye movements, irregular heart and respiratory rates, and relatively high levels of motor activity such as muscle twitches (Mirmiran et al., 2003; Peirano et al., 2003). This sleep stage appears essential for the initial development of multiple brain systems at ages equivalent to the human preterm period (Knoop et al., 2021). In young animals, deprivation of active sleep during critical periods of brain maturation is associated with subsequent loss of brain plasticity, as manifested by smaller brain size, reduced brain growth, and long-lasting behavioral and brain functional alterations (Frank et al., 2001; Dang-Vu et al., 2006; Blumberg et al., 2022).

However, the applicability of these findings to human preterm infants remains unknown. While several studies have linked decreased active sleep time during the preterm period to long-term cognitive impairments (Freudigman and Thoman, 1993; Arditi-Babchuk et al., 2009; Shellhaas et al., 2017; Bennet et al., 2018), the neural substrates underlying this association are still unclear. Furthermore, existing studies typically evaluate the sleep of preterm infants admitted to the NICU using behavioral observation or polysomnography. These conventional approaches allow sleep evaluation for only a few minutes to hours (Werth et al., 2017; Georgoulas et al., 2021), resulting in insufficient data to obtain stable sleep metrics. To bridge this gap, there is a need to design and implement automated methods for continuous sleep assessment over an extended period, ideally spanning multiple days.

In this context, the current study aimed to examine the association between active sleep and white matter development in preterm infants admitted to the NICU. We hypothesized that infants with more active sleep during their preterm period would exhibit larger white matter volume at term-equivalent age. To continuously measure sleep in the NICU, we developed an automated sleep stage classifier based on routinely monitored heart and respiratory rates.

Materials and Methods

Experimental design and study population

The present study included the following two cohorts: the algorithm cohort and the study cohort (see Fig. 1 for the overall study design).

The algorithm cohort was employed to develop an automated sleep stage classifier that enables continuous sleep stage assessment in the NICU over an extended period. To this end, the classifier was built using routinely monitored heart and respiratory rates. This cohort consisted of 25 preterm infants (12 females), with each infant undergoing up to 3 consecutive hours of visual sleep scoring and simultaneous monitoring of heart and respiratory rates at the NICU bedside.

The study cohort, consisting of 58 preterm infants (31 females), was used to investigate the sleep–brain associations. The sleep stages of these infants were measured using the automated classifier developed from the algorithm cohort. For each infant, sleep data were gathered over 5–7 consecutive days, a duration that has proven to be the minimum necessary to obtain reliable and stable estimates for sleep characteristics in older infants and children (Taylor et al., 2015; Camerota et al., 2018). Each included infant had less than 5 continuous hours of unrecorded heart and respiratory rate data throughout this duration. The sleep stage assessment was focused within 29–32 weeks (29 weeks + 0 days to 31 weeks + 6 days) of postmenstrual age (PMA). This specific period was chosen since the phase around 30 weeks represents a critical juncture for white matter reorganization, which can significantly affect its maturation (Dubois et al., 2014; Pittet et al., 2019). Moreover, each infant in the study cohort had an MRI scan at term-equivalent age (range, 39.9–44.1 weeks PMA).

Both cohorts excluded infants diagnosed with major congenital malformations and overt brain injury, defined as the presence of an intraventricular hemorrhage grade III, arterial ischemic stroke, venous infarction, posthemorrhagic ventricular dilatation, or (cystic) periventricular leukomalacia. In addition, infants who were receiving morphine and/or mechanical ventilation were excluded in both cohorts to eliminate their potential effects on sleep assessment.

All enrolled infants in the two cohorts were admitted to the NICU of the Wilhelmina Children's Hospital (Utrecht, The Netherlands). Ethical clearance for using patient data was granted by the Medical Research Ethics Committee (MREC) of the University Medical Centre (UMC) Utrecht (No. 21-066-C). Written informed consent was obtained from the parents for sleep observation for the algorithm cohort. Since MRI scanning at term-equivalent age and routine heart and respiratory rate monitoring are part of standard medical care in our NICU, the MREC Utrecht waived the need for written parental consent. All data were anonymized before being analyzed.

Figure 1. Study flowchart. PMA, postmenstrual age; dHCP, developing Human Connectome Project.

Sleep stage assessment

Heart and respiratory rate monitoring. For both cohorts, heart and respiratory rates were measured with a standard bedside patient monitor (IntelliVue MP70; Philips Medical Systems) and stored using in-house software (BedBase). The respiratory rate was recorded at a sampling rate of 0.4 Hz. The heart rate was recorded at either 0.4 or 1 Hz due to changes in software settings, and the data recorded at 1 Hz were subsequently downsampled to the lower sampling rate of 0.4 Hz to maintain consistency.

Visual sleep scoring. In the algorithm cohort, each infant received up to 3 consecutive hours of visual sleep scoring, conducted by three trained sleep observers. During each observation, one single observer was present at the infant's bedside in the NICU. The inter-observer reliability was assessed by Fleiss' kappa, yielding a κ value of 0.76. In cases of caregiving activities, observations were carried out whenever feasible. However, observers were required to suspend the observation if the simultaneous execution of care and observation proved difficult.

Four behavioral states (including active sleep, intermediate sleep, quiet sleep, and wakefulness) were visually scored using discrete 1 min epochs according to the criteria of a validated observational sleep scoring system for preterm infants (de Groot et al., 2022). The sleep observers' level of confidence in their scoring was represented by a confidence score added to each epoch, with a score of +1 denoting high confidence, 0 denoting medium confidence, and -1 denoting low confidence.

Automated sleep stage classification. Using visual sleep scoring data as ground truth, we first built an automated sleep stage classifier based on heart and respiratory rate signals within the algorithm cohort. To mitigate any bias caused by uncertainty, we exclusively included observed sleep stages with a confidence score of 1. This amounted to a total of 2,155 min of data. Intermediate sleep stages (113 min, 5%) were excluded due to their ambiguous definition and lack of distinct characteristics. In total, 2,042 min (equivalent to 34.0 h, with approximately 1% during caregiving events) of observational sleep data were used to develop the automated classifier for classifying active sleep, quiet sleep, and wakefulness.

A set of time-series features were calculated from heart and respiratory rates using 60, 180, and 480 s time windows ahead of each sleep observation epoch (including the observation epoch). The features could be grouped into three categories: basic statistics (mean, standard deviation, maximum, minimum, median, and interquartile range), nonlinear parameters (Higuchi fractal dimension and sample entropy), and derivative statistics (mean, standard deviation, maximum, and minimum of the first and second derivatives). We employed the two nonlinear parameters to quantify signal dynamics/complexity. They were chosen for their efficiency and ease of use.

To eliminate the adverse effects caused by different value ranges of different features, all extracted features were normalized to zero mean and unit variance (i.e., Z score normalization). The Z score normalized features were fed into a light gradient boosting machine (LightGBM) model to classify the visually scored sleep stages (Ke et al., 2017). This model was selected due to its excellent predictive performance and exceptional computational efficiency.

The LightGBM classifier was trained through a leave-one-subject-out cross-validation (LOSOVCV) procedure to evaluate its out-of-sample performance. The classification performance was measured by micro-averaged AUROC, weighted F1-score, and Cohen's kappa (κ) coefficient of agreement. To examine the robustness of the classifier against maturational effects on sleep, Pearson correlation coefficients were calculated between these performance metrics and PMA at the time of sleep observation.

The automated sleep stage classifier was then applied to the study cohort to assess infants' sleep stages for each recorded minute over 5–7 consecutive days during 29–32 weeks PMA. To address data gaps within these 5–7 d, we employed backfilling, followed by forward filling. However, to ensure the reliability of the results, any segments with data missing for more than 10 min were excluded from the subsequent

analyses. To describe infants' sleep architecture, we extracted four parameters: the total sleep time per 24 h, active sleep percentage of the total sleep time, quiet sleep percentage of the total sleep time, and percentage of awake time. The parameter of interest for subsequent regression analysis was active sleep percentage.

The sleep staging analyses were implemented using a machine learning package scikit-learn (version 0.23.2) within Python 3.8.5.

Structural brain analysis

MRI acquisition. For infants in the study cohort, MRI examinations were performed at term-equivalent age on a clinical 3-Tesla Philips Achieva scanner (Philips Healthcare) with a SENSE head coil. Structural T2-weighted images were obtained in the coronal plane using a turbo spin echo sequence (repetition time, 4,851 ms; echo time, 150 ms; in-plane resolution, 0.35×0.35 mm²; slice thickness, 1.2 mm). Vital signs were continuously monitored throughout the examination and transport, and a neonatologist or physician assistant was always present to check the infants' conditions. If necessary, the infants were sedated with 50–60 mg/kg oral chloral hydrate prior to scanning. To reduce movement artefacts, the infants were immobilized by a vacuum mattress during scanning. Double-layer hearing protection was provided for each infant with Minimuffs (Natus Europe) and earmuffs (EMs 4 kids).

After the MRI acquisition, image quality was checked by an experienced neonatologist (J.D.) blinded to patients' sleep characteristics. Only scans without large movement artefacts and/or overt brain injury (see the detailed definition in the Experimental design and study population section) were used for subsequent volumetric segmentation analysis.

Volumetric tissue segmentation. The structural T2-weighted images were processed using the neonatal structural processing pipeline of the developing Human Connectome Project (dHCP) (Makropoulos et al., 2018). Briefly, the dHCP pipeline automatically performs the following steps: bias correction, brain extraction, tissue segmentation, and volume estimation. Example segmentation performance of the dHCP on T2-weighted scans for preterm infants admitted to our NICUs can be found in a prior study (Lammertink et al., 2022).

Our primary volume of interest was total white matter volume. To enhance the interpretive context, we also measured total tissue volume (including all gray and white matter volumes) and merged volume of cerebrospinal fluid and ventricles. To minimize the impact of interindividual variation in brain size, the total volume of white matter was normalized using total tissue volume, and the merged volume of cerebrospinal fluid and ventricles was normalized using intracranial volume (including total tissue volume, cerebrospinal fluid, and ventricles).

Statistical analysis

Multiple linear regression models were built to investigate the associations between active sleep percentage (as the independent variable) and the three volumetric tissues (each acting as the dependent variable), respectively. For all three regression models, sex, GA at birth, PMA at the time of MRI scanning, and PMA at the start of sleep assessment were included as confounding covariates, given their potential influence on sleep and/or structural brain development. The birth weight was not used as a confounder due to its significant correlation with GA at birth ($R = 0.50$, $p < 0.001$), which remained significant even after being standardized for GA at birth and sex ($R = -0.37$, $p = 0.005$). Regression results were reported as standardized regression coefficients (β) with 95% confidence interval (CI). The significance level was set at $p < 0.05$. False discovery rate (FDR)-based procedure was used to adjust for multiple tests.

The statistical analyses were performed using R (version 4.2.2) within R studio (version 2023.03.0+386).

Data availability

Individual participant data (after de-identification) and codes are available on request from the corresponding author (J.D.). Any data sharing will be subject to meeting the Privacy Regulations of UMC Utrecht, the

General Data Protection Regulation, and the General Data Protection Regulation Implementation Act.

Results

Patient characteristics

The demographics and clinical information of the two cohorts are summarized in Table 1.

Sleep stage classification performance

The LightGBM classifier reached a mean AUROC of 0.87 (SD = 0.10, 95% CI 0.83–0.92), a mean F1-score of 0.75 (SD = 0.13, 95% CI 0.70–0.80), and a mean κ of 0.52 (SD = 0.23, 95% CI 0.42–0.62), indicating a superior sleep stage classification performance compared to existing automated sleep staging algorithms based on vital signs (mean κ = 0.38–0.43) (Werth et al., 2020; Sentner et al., 2022). We created a confusion matrix to describe the agreement between observed and predicted sleep stages, with the precision values (i.e., the proportion of predictions that are accurate) and the number of (in)accurate predictions presented (Fig. 2). The correct classes of active sleep, quiet sleep, and wakefulness

achieved precision values of 70%, 87%, and 85%, respectively. Given this good performance, it becomes feasible to further investigate the sleep–brain relationship since most of the predictions made by the classifier were correct.

No statistically significant associations were found between the classification performance and PMA at the time of sleep observation (for AUROC: $R = 0.15$, $p = 0.47$; for F1-score: $R = 0.17$, $p = 0.42$; for κ : $R = 0.12$, $p = 0.57$), suggesting that the automated classifier was robust against possible maturational effects on sleep.

Long periods of continuous sleep assessment

Using the trained LightGBM classifier, we assessed sleep stages within the study cohort. Out of the total data gathered, 1,095 min were excluded due to data gaps, resulting in a total of 571,787 min (equivalent to 9529.8 h) of sleep data. The average assessment time was 164.3 h (SD = 8.7; range, 124.4–168.0 h). Sleep parameters were extracted to describe these infants' sleep architecture (Table 2). Based on the assessment results, infants in the study cohort spent most of their time asleep (mean sleep percentage per 24 h = 90%, 21.6/24) during 29–32 weeks of PMA. On average, these infants spent 47% of their sleep time in active sleep and 53% in quiet sleep. Moreover, the long-duration estimated sleep percentages in the study cohort exhibited less variability (lower SD values) across individuals than the observed and predicted short-duration sleep data in the algorithm cohort. Additionally, the automated sleep stage classifier tends to identify more frequent transitions between sleep stages in comparison to observational sleep scoring, as indicated by shorter median bout lengths observed in the automatically derived sleep data (Table 2). Examples of sleep data in the algorithm cohort and study cohort are illustrated in Figure 3.

Brain volumes

In the study cohort, the mean normalized white matter volume was 42% (SD = 1%; range, 38–45%), the mean normalized volume of cerebrospinal fluid and ventricles was 24% (SD = 3%; range, 17–33%), and the mean total tissue volume was 366,582 mm³ (SD = 38,980 mm³; range, 218,105–443,751 mm³).

Associations between active sleep and brain volumes

As shown in Table 3 and Figure 4, a higher active sleep percentage was significantly associated with a larger white matter volume, after

Table 1. Patient characteristics

	Algorithm cohort (<i>n</i> = 25)	Study cohort (<i>n</i> = 58)
Female sex, <i>n</i> (%)	12 (48%)	31 (53%)
GA at birth, weeks	30.0 (1.7; 27.1–33.0)	27.2 (1.3; 24.6–29.6)
Birth weight, grams	1342 (365)	982 (212)
PMA at the time of sleep observation, weeks	31.4 (1.5; 29.0–33.9)	NA
PMA at the start of automated sleep assessment, weeks	NA	29.9 (0.5; 29.0–31.1)
PMA at the time of MRI scanning, weeks	NA	41.1 (0.7; 39.9–44.1)
Apgar score		
At 1st minute	6 (4, 7)	5 (3, 7)
At 5th minute	8 (6, 9)	8 (7, 9)
At 10th minute	8 (8, 9)	9 (8, 9)

Data are shown in *n* (%), mean (SD; range), mean (SD), or median (Q1, Q3). GA, gestational age; PMA, postmenstrual age; MRI, magnetic resonance imaging.

Figure 2. Confusion matrix for the automated sleep stage classifier. Percentages (and corresponding colors) in the confusion matrix denote the precision value and add to 100% per column. Percentages in the predicted W column adds to 101% due to rounding error. Numbers in brackets denote the count value of (in)correct predictions. AS, active sleep; QS, quiet sleep; W, wakefulness.

Table 2. Sleep characteristics

	Algorithm cohort (<i>n</i> = 25)		Study cohort (<i>n</i> = 58)
	Observed	Predicted	
Total sleep time, minutes	70 (21; 35–124)	77 (20; 47–126)	NA
Total sleep time per 24 h, hours	NA	NA	21.6 (0.4; 20.7–22.9)
Active sleep percentage of the total sleep time, %	54 (26; 6–95)	65 (17; 34–100)	47 (8; 26–66)
Quiet sleep percentage of the total sleep time, %	45 (26; 5–94)	35 (17; 0–66)	53 (8; 34–74)
Percentage of awake time, %	14 (15; 0–53)	5 (6; 0–18)	10 (2; 5–14)
Bout length of active sleep, minutes	4 (2, 7)	3 (1, 5)	2 (1, 4)
Bout length of quiet sleep, minutes	4 (2, 11)	2 (1, 4)	2 (1, 4)
Bout length of wakefulness, minutes	2 (1, 6)	1 (1, 3)	2 (1, 4)

Data are shown in mean (SD; range) or median (Q1, Q3).

Figure 3. Examples of sleep data. **A**, The observed and predicted sleep data of an infant from the algorithm cohort. Of note, the sleep data were not successive because only sleep stages with a confidence score of 1 were used for training the automated classifier. **B**, An example of machine learning-derived sleep pattern over 1 consecutive hour (from 10:00 A.M. to 11:00 A.M.) for an infant from the study cohort. AS, active sleep; QS, quiet sleep; W, wakefulness.

Table 3. Associations between active sleep percentage and volumetric tissues

	β	95% CI	Raw p -value (β)	FDR-adjusted p -value (β)
White matter	0.31	(0.09, 0.53)	0.007	0.021
Cerebrospinal fluid and ventricles	-0.28	(-0.55, -0.01)	0.046	0.046
Total tissue	0.27	(0.03, 0.51)	0.030	0.045

The effect sizes of the associations are shown as standardized regression coefficients (β) with 95% confidence interval (CI). The p -value (β) tests the null hypothesis that the regression coefficient (β) is zero. The significance level was set at $p < 0.05$. False discovery rate (FDR)-based procedure was used to adjust for multiple tests.

adjusting for potential confounding covariates ($\beta = 0.31$, 95% CI 0.09–0.53, FDR-adjusted p -value = 0.021). We also found that active sleep percentage had a significant negative relationship with merged volume of cerebrospinal fluid and ventricles and a significant positive relationship with total tissue volume (Table 3).

Discussion

This study investigated the relationship between active sleep and white matter development in human preterm infants. We assessed sleep stages for 58 preterm infants over 5–7 consecutive days during 29–32 weeks PMA using an automated sleep stage classifier that achieved a superior classification performance (AUROC = 0.87, F1-score = 0.75, $\kappa = 0.52$). The total volume of white matter at term-equivalent age was derived using the dHCP pipeline. Consistent with our hypothesis, the results revealed that preterm infants with higher percentages of machine learning-derived active sleep had significantly larger white matter volumes at term-equivalent age after adjusting for potential confounders.

The late second to third trimesters are known to be pivotal for the early development of human white matter (Kostović et al., 2021; Wilson et al., 2021). Preterm infants admitted to the NICU experience this crucial period in a busy and noisy environment, exposing them to various external factors that can potentially impair their white matter development. The positive association between active sleep and white matter maturation, as found in the current study, indicates that protecting preterm infants' sleep through routine monitoring in the NICU and subsequently adapting care according to the infants' sleep–wake rhythm could be beneficial. The automated sleep stage classifier developed in this study, as well as the recently published real-time sleep staging algorithm (Sentner et al., 2022), utilized routinely measured vital signs for sleep assessment. This eliminates the need for additional electrodes or the constant presence of an observer, making these techniques a practical and feasible option for routine sleep monitoring in the NICU.

Unlike conventional, time-consuming methods that offer a brief snapshot of sleep, automated algorithms allow for continuous, long-duration sleep monitoring. This helps to yield more stable estimates of sleep quantity and quality, possibly providing a more accurate reflection of preterm infants' sleep architecture during their NICU stay. This inference is substantiated by the lower variability observed in the long-duration estimated sleep parameters in the study cohort compared to the short-duration sleep data in the algorithm cohort.

The findings of this study also align with previous animal research, emphasizing the importance of active sleep in the initial stages of brain plasticity and development (Frank et al., 2001; Dang-Vu et al., 2006; Blumberg et al., 2022). While the specific mechanisms by which active sleep promotes early brain

Figure 4. The relationship between active sleep percentage and white matter volume. **A**, The raw relationship. **B**, The relationship after adjusting for covariates. The scatter plot in **B** is based on partial residuals from multiple linear regression models, with both active sleep percentage and white matter volume being adjusted for confounding covariates (and thus their values can be negative). The solid line indicates linear regression fit, and the shaded area indicates 95% confidence interval. The Pearson correlation coefficient (R) is shown in each scatter plot.

development are not yet fully understood, several hypotheses have been proposed (Del Rio-Bermudez and Blumberg, 2018; Blumberg et al., 2020; Knoop et al., 2021; Lokhandwala and Spencer, 2022). Among these, the most prevalent hypothesis posits that active sleep promotes the expression of delta-brush oscillations within and between cortical and subcortical structures, thereby contributing to brain development at the network level (Del Rio-Bermudez and Blumberg, 2018). Notably, the significant positive association observed between active sleep and white matter volume in the present study lends partial support to this hypothesis, given the essential role of white matter in mediating brain connections (Filly and Fields, 2016).

Furthermore, delta-brush oscillations are a hallmark of preterm electroencephalogram and constitute the primary component of spontaneous activity transients (SATs). They can be triggered by myoclonic twitches during active sleep (Milh et al., 2007; Molnár et al., 2020), and occur more frequently in active sleep than in quiet sleep before 32 weeks (Kidokoro, 2021; Wang et al., 2023). The increased numbers of delta-brushes or SATs have been linked to larger brain volumes in human preterm infants (Benders et al., 2015; De Wel et al., 2021), which is in line with the findings of the present work.

White matter dysmaturation often co-occurs with reduced total tissue volume and increased cerebrospinal fluid and ventricular volumes (Keunen et al., 2012; Anderson et al., 2017). Given this, the observed positive correlation between active sleep percentage and total tissue volume, as well as the negative

correlation of active sleep with cerebrospinal fluid and ventricular volumes, strengthens the notion that active sleep may have a positive impact on white matter development.

Several limitations of the current study warrant mention. First, this study was conducted in a clinical setting where various clinical factors could potentially influence sleep–brain associations. While we included several key confounding factors to mitigate bias, residual confounders might still affect our findings. Second, the current sample consisted uniformly of relatively healthy infants, leading to a less diversity in both sleep and brain measures. Future research might consider targeting infants under different clinical conditions. Third, it is crucial to note that a correlation identified by regression analysis does not imply causation. To verify if an increase in white matter volume results from more active sleep, further intervention research utilizing randomized controlled trials is needed.

We identified several promising directions for future research. Given the rapid maturational changes in preterm infants, a week-by-week analysis of sleep characteristics throughout their NICU stay would help to develop a more comprehensive understanding of how sleep and brain development are intertwined and provide more accurate assessments of the impacts of various clinical factors. In particular, the influence of kangaroo care, parental visitation, nutrition, and stress on infants' sleep needs to be investigated in future studies (Volpe, 2019).

Considering the perfectly negative correlation between active and quiet sleep percentages of total sleep time, our results also indicated that less quiet sleep would be linked to better white matter development. However, it is important to acknowledge that a deficiency in quiet sleep might not be advantageous for the initial development of the brain, given that quiet sleep is a vital part of the sleep pattern of preterm infants (Blumberg et al., 2022). Further research is required to determine the optimal balance between the two sleep stages.

Furthermore, the automated classifier developed in the current study appears to overestimate the amount of active sleep (65%) when compared to the observed data (54%). Nonetheless, it identified a smaller proportion of active sleep (mean, 47%) in comparison to previous studies (60–80%) that evaluated sleep over shorter and less disruptive periods (DiPietro et al., 1996; Werth et al., 2017; Georgoulas et al., 2021). Given that this study is the first to consistently monitor sleep over an extended period of 5–7 consecutive days, it highlights the need for more long-duration sleep studies to validate our findings.

Lastly, agreement regarding the normal range for white matter volume in full-term infants is lacking at present due to variations in technical and methodological approaches across various studies (Hüppi et al., 1998; Kuklisova-Murgasova et al., 2011; Kvantá et al., 2021). To determine the precise amount of active sleep required for preterm infants to achieve white matter development comparable to that of their full-term peers, it is recommended that future research employs a prospective case-control design.

In summary, we reported a significant positive association between the percentage of machine learning-derived active sleep during the preterm period and white matter volume at term-equivalent age in preterm infants. This discovery provides new insights into the role of active sleep in early human brain development, confirming and extending findings from animal research. Our findings further indicate the potential benefit of integrating automated sleep monitoring into routine caregiving practices in NICU settings. In doing so, caregivers can plan

elective care according to an infant's sleep cycles, thus promoting optimal early brain development.

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